

Examining The Role Of Instructional Leaders And Their Effects On Teacher Performance And, Organization Citizenship Behavior In Educational Sector Of Pakistan: Teacher's Self-Efficacy As A Mediating Factor

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 15, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: June 16, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Instructional Leader, Teacher's Self-efficacy, Teachers' performance, and OCB</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8048191</p>	<p><i>This research showed a link between instructional leadership and teacher job performance. Although knowledge-based leadership is well developed in Western societies, there is still room for it in developing countries. Employees go above and beyond their regular duties when leaders have strong instructional practices. Additionally, teachers' self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between instructional leadership and employee outcomes, the study was conducted to close the existing knowledge gap. Original data from the education sector, including colleges and schools in Pakistan and the State of AJ&K, was used in current research. 260 individual-level data points have been gathered for analysis (employees). In this study, EFA, CFA, and SEM factor analyses were carried out. The findings provided substantial support for the put forth theoretical framework. By putting into consideration this descriptive study, underdeveloped nations will enhance their leadership skills and educational environment.</i></p>

Introduction

Over the last half-century, the role of school leaders has shifted dramatically in the global educational landscape. This line of investigation has progressed to the point where as, few countries around the world encourage principals to actively participate in the role of instructional leader (Thesin , 2019). Over the last half-century, the role of school leaders has shifted dramatically in the global education landscape Hallinger& Wang, (2016)and successful leadership practices varies across organizational contexts.Over the past three decades, academic literature on instructional leadership (IL) and its impacts on teachers' commitment, satisfaction, and retention have been widely discussed (Boyce & Bowers, 2018). Accordingly,previous study showed that instructional leadership behaviour has a positive impact on student's achievement than other types of leadership behaviour (Louis et al., 2010). This leadership style emphasis involving teachers in decision-making. Leadership is essential for improving organisational performance in terms of educational outcomes, and much emphasis has been placed on how leaders can play an important role in community development by focusing on their respective fields. In particular, instructional leadership is defined as the strategies and actions taken by the principal and other institutional leaders to promote, intensify, and ensure consistency in classroom instruction and learning (Wang &Hallinger, 2015).

Instructional leadership, individuals' performance, citizenship behavior, self-efficacy with knowledge management, and e-learning are all interrelated concepts that play important roles in the modern educational landscape.Recent research has looked into how instructional leadership can be used in institutions to support knowledge management and e-learning. While relevant social and demographic factors have changed in recent years, higher education opportunities have yet to catch up with current and future trends (Ogbodoakum, Ayub&Abiddin,2022).Those institutions consider instructional leadership, they notice visible changes in their subordinates, such as high self-efficacy and optimistic employee performance. Current study attempts to investigate the role of instructional leadership on teacher job performance. One recent study found that individual's confidence allows them to learn from their instructors while maintaining their level of performance (Phan, 2023). Furthermore, higher education creates a learning environment in the classroom to encourage their staff to participate in OCB (Kang et al., 2020).

Another study revealed that instructional leadership practices like providing professional development opportunities for teachers, motivating their confidence, and e-learning will contribute to effective knowledge management and e-learning (Chen &Wang & Liu, 2021). Likewise, instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on knowledge management, which is mediated by self-efficacy, which in turn has a significant positive effect on teachers' intention to share their knowledge (Tien & Fu, 2021). In education sector, knowledge management positively associated with instructional leadership. Furthermore, knowledge

management improves performance significantly (Kim, S., 2022; Wang, Q., & Li, L., 2022). Although the evidence base for instructional leadership has not yet been fully developed in several countries, it is growing in Asia (Hallinger et al. 2018). This body of literature seeks to present a current examination of the empirical foundations for instructional leadership in Pakistan. Previous research indicates that principals of schools and colleges have little direct influence on students, but they do have a strong positive influence on teaching and non-teaching staff, which increases their behaviours and beliefs about the job and, as a result, improves teachers' job performance (Ismail et al., 2018). School leaders use instructional leadership practices that have a positive and significant relationship with teachers' competencies (Hendriks & Steen, 2012). Instructional leaders, as principals work closely with teachers in the classroom to monitor their development and learning strategies, which are strongly correlated with teachers' performance (Knapp et al., 2014). Despite this, research showed that administrators with stronger instructional skills encourage teachers to perform at a higher level by communicating and modelling it. Although there is evidence linking school leadership to improvements in teacher attitudes and practices (Lijuan & Hallinger, 2016). Similarly, current study highlights the lack of evidence linking principals' instructional leadership (PIL) with classroom teaching and teachers' job performance. The primary objective of this research is to look into the relationship between instructional leadership and teachers performance. Moreover, investigations of organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) have grown in the literature on educational research and school effectiveness (Nasra & Heilbrunn, 2016). Organ (1988, p. 4) defines OCB as "discretionary behaviour that is not directly or openly acknowledged by the formal incentive structure and that improves the company's overall effectiveness." Several studies on the subject have focused on the question of whether elements promote OCB. Many of these studies have discovered that a strong leader has a positive impact on employee's OCB. Teachers who engage in OCB are influenced by their leaders who possess instructional leadership qualities. Accordingly, OCB is defined as teachers who go above and beyond their formal job responsibilities with the school, the teaching staff, and the students in order to advance the organization and achieve its objectives (Somech & Oplatka, 2014). Likewise, research has shown that leadership philosophies are closely related to OCB (Nasra & Heilbrunn, 2016). The performance of teachers and organisational citizenship behaviours of teachers are significantly impacted by more recent studies on leaders' behaviours (Arar & Nasara, 2019), which accelerates organisational progress. The educational sector in underdeveloped countries like Pakistan faces new challenges as it ushers in a new era while operating in a complex and competitive environment. The willingness of teachers to go above and beyond their formal jobs and demonstrate their performance is crucial to the success of this reputable industry.

According to earlier studies, when leaders are informed, employees show more pro-social behaviour, such as OCB (Bedi et al., 2016). Leaders are viewed as having a significant impact on how employees behave due to their special position as providers of OCB-related rewards (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Citizenship-minded employees, as we all know, want to take a different approach to the growth of the institutions. Those workers feel that their leaders care about their welfare, they will want to reciprocate the behaviour by performing extra tasks as a token of appreciation, free of charge (Joo & Jun Joo, 2017). This study concentrated on organisational citizenship behaviours, which are essential for the survival of institutions. Leaders especially instructional leadership, which has received little attention in social science literature have a positive influence on these informal behaviours. Thus, second objective of study is to examine the relationship between instructional leader and organizational citizenship behavior. Furthermore, current study sought to understand the hidden factors that have been identified as to how leadership practices relate to subordinates' performance in order to motivate employees to engage in discretionary behaviour (OCB) outside of the scope of their regular duties. As a result, individuals like professors, lecturers and teachers exhibit better workplace behaviours and outcomes. According to Bandura's social cognitive theory (1986), self-efficacy beliefs play a crucial role in determining an individual's motivation, behavior, and performance. In this theory, self-efficacy is viewed as a mediating variable between environmental factors, personal factors, and behavior. Recent research has continued to support the role of self-efficacy as a mediator between leadership and performance (Li, Zhang & Li 2020). Individuals with high efficacy positively viewed their leaders' instructions that positively increase their performance (Duyar et al., 2013).

Another study investigated the role of self-efficacy as a mediator between ethical leadership and employee voice behavior (van Dam & Oreg, 2019). Similarly, a study by Schyns & Schilling (2013) found that self-efficacy mediated the relationship between leader-member exchange and job performance. Moreover, individual's belief in their ability to perform a specific task, has been identified as an important factor that mediates the relationship between leadership and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Recent research has supported the role of self-efficacy as a mediator between leadership and OCB. This suggests that leaders who exhibit transformational behaviors can enhance employee self-efficacy beliefs, which, in turn, can promote OCB (Kim, Im, & Kim 2019).

Similarly, a study by Demirtas & Akdogan (2015) investigated the role of self-efficacy as a mediator between ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior in Turkey. The study looked at how employees' self-efficacy affects their organisational citizenship behaviour and performance (Mahipalan, Sheena & Muhammed,

2019). Utilizing a self-efficacy theory, our study discusses the mediating mechanism of teacher's self-efficacy (TSE), referring to an employee's belief that he/she has the ability to perform successfully and positive outcomes like OCB (He et al., 2020). In the present study, students' self-efficacy refers to the teacher's beliefs in their abilities to carry out a specific learning task provided by their leaders/head of institutions. These beliefs motivate them to increase their performance and perform extra role activities. Current research identified that self-efficacy as a strong linking mechanism between instructional leadership and performance of employees. Social cognitive theory by Bandura's (1991), endorses instructional leadership, acts as an indicator of teacher's efficacy and belief, increasing teacher competency and output at work. Leadership roles are directly related to teachers' effectiveness and indirectly to students' academic success, which may result in high performance from teachers (Hoy & Tarter, 2011). Indeed, instructional leaders' strategies and teachers' self-efficacy are positively related, which has a positive impact on institutional performance (Hallinger et al., 2018). As a result, teachers' self-efficacy is a useful strategy for gaining a better understanding of competency in classroom management, student engagement, and improving teachers' performance (Bellibas & Liu, 2016). Moreover, self-efficacy, a social cognition construct (social learning) which refers to a person's self-beliefs in his or her ability to perform specific tasks that has been shown to be a reliable predictor of task performance (Wood & Bandura, 1990). Self-efficacy also influence on personal goal setting (Appelbaum & Hare, 1996). Previous literature demonstrated that self-efficacy of employees during working hours plays as an important linking mechanism that will enhance their performance as well as boost them to do some extra effort for their institutions. Indeed, the role of self-efficacy as the mediator has not been widely debated with instructional leadership and teachers performance as well as with organizational citizenship behavior. Self-efficacy has been linked to happiness and psychological distress in past studies (Loton & Waters, 2017). With clear instructions from their leaders and bosses, highly self-centered employees try to contribute their ideas and energy to the organization in addition to their job duties. Many findings have clarified the importance to pay attention to the importance of teachers' self-efficacy as a mediating mechanism. Bandura, (1986) suggested that, when employees have a high level of self-efficacy (i.e., believing that personal efforts would lead to positive expected outcomes and avoid negative ones) and when they believe that they have supportive leader/boss, they will feel more comfortable to accept challenges at work and to engage in organization citizenship behavior. They may even be proactive in setting challenging goals for changing the status quo and pursue the performance (Zhang Y. et al., 2018). Meanwhile, employees with a high self-efficacy tend to make extra efforts (e.g., extra work hours, double tasks) to achieve better performance (Fang et al., 2019). When employees conduct extra-role behaviors with self-driven will, we assume that they have to adopt OCBs. High level of confidence is therefore created on employees to be helpful, committed in additional responsibilities, and to adopt different forms of OCB (Bolino et al., 2015). In view, OCB may make employees feel less stressed and threatened, which will increase employees' internal self-efficacy. Based on this context, the aim of the present study is to investigate the role of teachers self-efficacy beliefs as a mediator between instructional leadership and teachers job performance as well as self-efficacy as a mediator between instructional leadership and organizational citizenship behavior in educational sector of Pakistan. Therefore, third objective of current study is to examine teachers' self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between instructional leadership and teachers' job performance as well as with organizational citizenship behavior.

Theoretical Background & Literature Review

Instructional Leadership and Teachers' Job Performance

Leadership is the bedrock of any organization seeking to improve the effectiveness of a learning environment. This efficacy is amplified, especially in colleges and schools, which are viewed as sources of knowledge generation. Similarly, instructional principal leadership is an important phenomenon from the last three decades that has an indirect influence on school and student performance (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985). According to Boyce & Boyers (2018), leaders are those who empower teachers to participate in school decision-making. Many countries' new education policies have codified instructional leadership responsibilities into job qualifications, selection criteria, training programmes, and evaluation standards for school leaders (Fromm et al., 2016). It is becoming more difficult to find settings in 2016 where principals are not pushed to use 'instructional leadership' (Bellibas et al., 2016a). Principals of colleges and schools have a responsibility as instructional leaders to improve the overall performance of the organisation; however, there is no short cut; they must empower their teaching staff to teach and learn their students to the highest standards (Bafadal, 2016b), which will improve their staff's performance. Previous research has found that leadership positions have a significant and positive impact on teacher performance. As a result, improving headmasters'/principals' leadership qualities will improve teacher performance (Andriani, Kesumawati & Kristiawan, 2018). Previous research has found that principal leadership has a significant positive influence on teachers' job duties. The teacher is an essential component of the educational process and must perform admirably. The performance of teachers is frequently evaluated. Two examples of efforts we can make to improve teacher performance are principals/headmasters collaborating with school supervisors to provide professional education and

administration supervision of learning in the classroom (Yuliandri, kristiawan, 2016). Suharjono, (2012: 6) discussed the factors that can influence a teacher's performance, such as leadership and motivation at work. As a result, if universities, colleges and schools want teachers/ lecturers to perform well and at a high level, they should consider factors such as leadership roles and practices that will motivate them. To achieve synchronization between teacher performance and community development, leaders must take an active role in instructing their followers to form duties in this manner. Indeed, the leadership of certified teachers and principals was significantly related to teacher performance (Hartiwi, Kozlova & Masitoh, 2020). Study hypothesized based on the preceding discussion, which is supported by previous research.

H1: There is a positive relationship between Instructional leadership and teachers' performance in higher education institutions and post graduate colleges.

Instructional Leadership and organizational citizenship behavior

Organization citizenship behaviour (OCB) was defined by Katz & Kahn, (1996) as an individual's discretionary behaviour in the absence of official norms and regulations. Similarly, leadership theories typically contend that OCB is a personality trait, a social response to supervisory behaviour, and a likely reaction of the individual to superiors' behaviour or other motivating factors in the workplace (Somech, & Khorana, 2017). These ideas could imply that OCB leaders have a significant impact on teachers' willingness to assist outside of their professional responsibilities (Somech & Oplatka, 2014). They assist them in developing their team's strengths as well as good coping skills in everyday situations, increasing their desire to demonstrate citizenship behaviours in order to improve the team's and organisational effectiveness (Heled et al., 2015). Furthermore, few elementary and secondary school teachers go above and beyond their typical job responsibilities, and the educational sector requires individuals who actively participate in the learning process, which is referred to as organisational civic behaviour (Eddleston et al., 2018; Gupta & Sharma, 2018). Social exchange processes that can occur in leader-follower relationships can play a role in inducing OCBs in employees (Elches., Ruiz Palomino, & Linuesa-Langreo, 2020), as supported by social learning theory (Bandura, 1977) and Blau's social exchange theory (Elches, Palomino, & Linuesa-Langreo, 2020). According to this theory, a strong leadership position encourages a leader's interaction with his or her subordinates (Madison & Eva, 2019). According to the current study, instructional leadership at universities and colleges is a viable source for improving the OCB, and leader integrity may drive employees to reciprocate with discretionary, positive actions (Guchait et al., 2016). Thus;

H2: There is a positive relationship between instructional leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour in higher education institutions.

The role of self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between IL and teacher's performance

An individual's sense of self-efficacy has a significant influence on their actions, thought processes, and performance (Bandura, 1977). Teacher efficacy is defined as a person's belief in the development of learning and the performance of the teacher's work in a learning environment. Over the last two decades, there has been a growing body of research demonstrating a positive relationship between self-efficacy and leadership (Hosseingholizadeh, Hashemi, & Kouhsari, 2017). Preliminary studies examined the role of school leadership and collective teacher efficacy in increasing student achievement levels (Salazar, 2014). Principals can influence teacher efficacy by articulating an exciting vision of learning for the school, setting attainable goals, clarifying teacher standards, and supporting teacher learning and performance, according to several reports (Calik et al., 2012).

Furthermore, empirical evidence suggested that teachers' self-efficacy is a factor influencing teacher success in the educational systems of eastern cultures (Chen, 2017). Teachers' self-efficacy is defined as "respect and confidence placed in them not only by students and parents, but also through university training and instruction, as well as instruction provided by their key leaders, particularly institutional leaders." Teachers' self-efficacy is seen as a mediator in the interaction between ILs and teacher professional learning (Liu & Hallinger, 2018). The concept of instructional leadership emphasizes the significance of teachers' efficacy in forging a connection between their leadership practices and job performance.

One of the past research showed that principals are not directly involved in school and student learning, they do have a direct influence on classroom teachers therefore, teachers' self-efficacy, considered as more powerful tool of establishing a link between ILs and teacher performance and school achievement (Duyar et al., 2013). According to a statistical study, collective teacher self-efficacy serves as a significant mediator in the relationship between instructional leadership and teachers' intention (Da'as, 2019). Teachers' leadership influences, as well as instructional leaders' improved efficacy of their staff members (Qadach, Schechter, & Da'a, 2019). Similarly, instructional leadership that affects the learning climate has a direct positive impact on teachers' self-efficacy (Ma & Marion, 2019). Employees with high efficacy are more at ease with their dependence and are more willing to take risks and try new things, which promotes the cooperative behaviour required to cultivate high performance (Tschannen-Moran & Gareis, 2015). The most cooperative relationship between leadership and teacher self-efficacy levels prime focus, allowing teachers to take risks and improve

their performance (Qian & Walker, 2014). Thus on the basis of existing literature , current study hypothesized as;

H3: Teachers' self-efficacy mediates the relationship between ILs and teacher's performance.

Self-efficacy as a Mediator between IL and OCB

Self-efficacy refers to people's confidence in their ability to do their jobs well. According to social learning theory by Rotters, (1982) people's level of confidence in their abilities whether physical or intellectual and requires them to perform duties outside of their job description that demonstrate positive workplace behaviours such behaviors is known as organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Kim, Hwang, & Lee 2019; De Simone, Planta, & Cicotto, 2018). It refers to an employee's actions that go above and beyond the formal requirements of his or her job (Ocampo et al., 2018). Few studies demonstrated that self-efficacy will influence OCB of employees (Ersoy, Derous, Born & van der Molen, 2015). Indeed, one of the statistical regression analysis revealed that instructional leadership can predict teachers' efficacy, this study identified that employees self-efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between leadership and organization commitment (Cansoy, Parlar & Polatcan, 2020). As a result, to reform and motivate teachers, leaders employ a variety of leadership styles (Al- Mahdy, Emam, & Hallinger, 2018). Collective efficacy beliefs and instructional leadership behaviours among teachers both contribute to school effectiveness (Blatti, Clinton, & Graham, 2018). It has been reported that principals act as a leaders promote teacher collaboration that increase teacher efficacy (Mosoge, Challens, & Xaba, 2018). Accordingly, teachers' high efficacy promotes high levels of collaboration and synergy among instructors.

Among the tasks of institutional leaders in this situation are organizing instructional activities and changing the learning environment (Hallinger et al., 2017). Self-efficacy fosters a sense of responsibility in students while increasing their awareness of difficulties that arise during the course of their work (Chu & Garcia, 2018). Their self-assurance fosters citizenship behaviour that enables them to solve problems. Previous studies discussed that teachers' encouragement in OCB is based on their self-efficacy; those with high efficacy demonstrate extra-role behaviours at work as a result of supportive leadership (Srivastava & Madan, 2017). Moreover, teachers who have a high level of self-confidence engage in extra-role behaviour as a result of the exchange of relationships between individual employees and their leadership, is consistent with this (Zeinabadi & Salehi, 2011). Their level of effectiveness balances the exchange of relationships between them, and these particular employees, namely teachers, can plan and carry out initiatives to involve in additional roles and good citizenship behaviour, increasing organisational effectiveness (Choong, Ng, & Na. 2019). As a result of the preceding discussion and empirical support, we hypothesised as follows:

H4: Teachers' self-efficacy mediates in the relationship between ILs and organization citizenship behavior.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Sr#	Variables' Name	Variables As
1)	Instructional Leadership (ILs)	Independent Variable
2)	Teachers' Self-efficacy (THE)	Mediator
3)	Teachers' Job Performance (TJP)	Dependent variable
4)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)	Dependent Variable

Research Methods

The following research methods and techniques were used in this study to investigate the answer to the desired question.

Research Design

This study employs the hypothetical deductive method, which means that previous literature and theories were used to develop hypotheses, which were then tested. Because quantitative research is the most effective in producing quality results for a large population, this research is also quantitative, which aided in linking the variables.

To test the hypothesis for this study, we gathered information from key figures in Pakistan's educational community, including universities and colleges teaching and non-teaching staff. An effective research design is used in social science research to increase the study's effectiveness. The two fundamental types of research are qualitative and quantitative (Wiersma & Jurs, 2005). De Vaus (2001) asserts that quantitative research design is the most reliable and beneficial, which is why the current study employed quantitative methodology.

The findings reported in the current paper arose during the analysis of data in a study focused on understanding how Instructional leadership practices impact on teachers' performance as well on developing organizational citizenship behavior and how self-efficacy mediates among them? In analyzing the data, it became clear that the degrees to which principals/instructional leader changed their instructional leadership practice were influenced by the qualities of the principal supervisor/ principal partnership. As a result, we concluded that the relational qualities of the principal supervisor and the principal deserved additional focus and attention, while not one of our original research foci. As such, for this paper, we revisited the data to answer the following questions:

RQ1. Does instructional leadership positively relate with teachers' performance and organizational citizenship behavior of employees?

RQ2. Does self-efficacy of teachers mediate in the relationship between instructional leadership and teachers' performance?

RQ3. Does self-efficacy of employees teachers mediate in the relationship between instructional leadership and organizational citizenship behavior?

Study setting and Procedure

The nation or state chosen for the study, "Islamabad, Rawalpindi and State of Azad Jammu & Kashmir," had a history of emphasizing the growth of principals' instructional leadership. The educational sector gave us a lot of pertinent information that was impartial in nature so we could collect data from various institutions across the nation.

The primary researcher for this study gathered data on public and private post-graduate colleges and universities in order to compile pertinent information. Employees, both teaching and non-teaching staff, participated in a self-administrative adopted questionnaire between May and August 2022 (the study's beginning month). The primary quantitative techniques to comprehend the relationship between and among variables of interest are study design and sample author usage.

Furthermore, when gathering data, we took into account demographic factors like age, gender, education, and position held, etc. The goal of the current study was to focus on the demographic characteristics of each respondent in order to accurately collect data and determine how leadership actually influences employee behaviour. Current research used time-lag design to reduce the biased data and three time-lag(T) was more preferable. T1 data was collected for demographic and instructional leadership, T2 data was gathered for employee self-efficacy, and T3 data was gathered for TP and OCB. The back of each questionnaire has been coded in order to collect the same respondents across all time lags. After the entire process had been successfully completed, the file was assembled by matching all similar codes. Two of our research team's members collected all of the data. Using SPSS software, all questionnaires collected during our observations were coded.

Therefore, 260 self-administrative questionnaires of HEIs employees in Rawalpindi, Islamabad, and the state of Azad Jammu and Kashmir was conducted. In the current study, women were used as a prior sample. The educational sector was chosen because it is Pakistan's second largest contributor to the economy.

Measurements/ Instrumentation

Questionnaires have been used in research to collect quantitative data. Studies had previously validated the scales used to rate the four focal components. The seven-point Likert scale was used to evaluate each measure because it is more reliable and commonly used in social science research. The seven-point scale is more important than other Likert scales, according to Preston and Colman (2000) and Ali et al. (2016). We also considered a 7-point Likert scale with a 0-6 scale (Van Vaerenbergh & Thomas, 2013).

Instructional/ Principal Leadership

To assess instructional leadership, the Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale (PIMRS) teacher short form of Hallinger (2013) was used, with 22 questions ranging from 0-(Never), 1- (Almost Never), 2- (Sometimes), 4-(Frequently), 5-(Almost Always), and 6-(Almost Always) (Always). The short-form instrument had a reliability of .94, while the three dimensions had a reliability of .90 to .93, according to Aziz et al. (2014).

Teacher's self-efficacy

Friedman and Kass (2002) developed a 33-item teacher self-efficacy scale with Cronbach's alpha reliability scores ranging from .88 to .90 on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 7.

Organization citizenship behavior

The five dimensions of OCB suggested by Organ (1988) are employed in this study since they are the most extensively used in organizational studies, according to academics (Gonzalez & Garazo, 2006). Based on five key dimensions, twenty measures were utilized to determine the level of citizenship behaviors among subordinates. The OCB aspects were measured using a Likert-style scale with anchors ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree) (Strongly Agree).

Teachers Job performance

Teachers' job performance 18 items, 7 points Likert scale which was used by (Yusoff et al., 2013) with reliability of all items are 0.80 that range from 0 (Never) to 6 (Always).

Control variables.

One of the five control factors in the current study was age (1=20-30yrs, 2=31-40yrs, 3=41-50yrs, 4=over 50yrs). Gender (1=male, 2=female), education (1=bachelor, 2=Masters, 3=M-phil, 4=PhD), marital status (1=unmarried, 2=married), and tenure (1=1-5yrs, 2=6-10yrs, 3=11-20yrs, 4=over 20 yrs).

Results

Current research analyzed the data using a variety of statistical techniques. After receiving data, through SPSS-21 checked the reliability (Cronbach alpha) of each variable to confirm that meets the threshold value (.6) or not. Result identified that Instructional leadership had .96, teacher self-efficacy had .98, teacher performance had .95 with 25 items, and OCB has 20 items with a .96 alpha value respectively that meets standard to use these measurements for further process.

Exploratory Factor Analysis.

EFA is a useful technique for data reduction, identifying latent variables, and exploring the underlying structure of large datasets. It can also be used to validate hypothesis or test theories (Norris & Lecavaler, 2010). Current research study conducted exploratory factor analysis before testing hypothesis. It has been performed with the help of statistical package for social science (SPSS-21). The current theoretical model initially includes four variables. To analyze EFA, principle component analysis method has been used that explains maximum portion of variance in the original variable. Moreover, Eigen value 0.02 has been used that explains how much factors need to be extracted? In order to resolve high correlation problem, current study used orthogonal rotation that maintained axis at 90 degrees. Moreover the statistical significance of factors has been classified on their magnitude. The factors loading less than +.03 have been deleted. There are 22 items of instructional leadership. Due to cross loading and less than +.03 three items of IL has been deleted i.e IL4, IL10 and IL15. Teacher's self-efficacy with 33-items has been extracted and result found that few items instead of loading on their own factor load on factor 1 and 4 with +.01 value so better to delete i.e TSE7, TSE10, TSE19, TSE25 and TSE27. Similarly, we have checked the extracted values of teachers job performance and result showed that out of 18 items three items deleted due to not load on its factor i.e TJP3, TJP12 and TJP16. Organizational citizenship behavior with 20 items, four items due to less than +.03 as well as load on factor 1 and 2 deleted these are OCB1, OCB5, OCB18 and OCB19.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis.

After identified the instruments, we have further confirmed the validity of each measure. For that confirmatory factor analysis through AMOS has been done. A few items have cross-loadings during CFA and did not load on their variables. Due to a lack of loading on its factor, three instructional leadership items, IL8, IL11, and IL20, had to be removed. TJP5 & TJP7 have minimal loading below, which is inline with teachers' performance. The model's fitness has been evaluated using the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), incremental fit index (IFI), Tucker-Lewis coefficient (TLI), and comparative fit index (CFI). All values showed in the below mentioned table.

Table 1: Confirmatory Factor Analysis of the Measurement Model

	Chi-Square	df	CMIN/DF	RMSEA	IFI	TLI	CFI
Initial model	2338.577	1445	1.628	0.050	0.912	0.886	0.901
Modified model	2322.554	1440	1.590	0.047	0.881	0.899	0.870

The table above shows several values of the initial model based on criteria such as RMSEA.050, IFI.912, TLI.886 and CFI.901. Although several alterations were made to obtain the goodness of the model fit, there were only a few chances to obtain new values. All of the adjusted values satisfy the threshold condition, enhancing the model's validity for hypothesis testing (Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2013). After running the model, the RMSEA =.047, which is less than .05, identified the model's fitness, and the IFI=.881, TLI=.88, and CFI=.88 all met the threshold values that determined the model's fitness for hypothesis testing. It means that the current research model showed validity of all variables and each item in the variables except few items that had been deleted to save the path model for errors. Those items that showed cross loading due to various reasons that might be due to lack of understanding of respondents or might be similar statements of different variables.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation between all research variables is depicted in the table below. The relationship between the variables in this study should be analyzed using Pearson correlation, where $r = +1$ to -1 . The table showed a significant and favourable correlation between teacher self-efficacy and instructional leadership ($r=.333$, $p.01$). There is a significant positive relationship between ILs and TJP and values ($r=.686$, $p.05$) as well as between teachers' leadership and citizenship behaviour ($r=.532$, $p.01$). Teachers' self-efficacy and performance were found to be positively correlated ($r=.442$, $p.05$). Significant OCB values are also correlated with teacher job performance ($r=.445$, $p.01$). According to this model, organisational citizenship behaviour was found to be significantly correlated with teachers' job performance ($r=.233$, $p.05$).

Table 2 : Correlation Analyses

Sr#	Variables	ILs	TSE	TJB	OCB
1	Instructional leadership	1			
2	Teachers' job efficacy	.333*	1		
3	Teachers' job performance	.686**	.442**	1	
4	Organization-citizenship behavior	.532*	.445*	.233**	1

$p^* < .01$ & $p^{**} < .05$, IL= Instructional Leadership, TSE= Teachers self-efficacy, TJB= Teachers Job Performance, OCB= Organization citizenship behavior

Hypothesis Testing

H1: There is a positive relationship between instructional leadership and teachers' job performance in higher education institutions.

H2: There is a positive relationship between instructional leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour in higher education institutions.

T3: Direct Path Analysis

S#	Structural Path	β	S. E	P-value
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H1	IL → TJP	.45	.086	.012
H2	IL → OCB	.39	.005	.004

***= $P < .001$, β represent un-standardized regression coefficients, S. E= Standard Error

Interpretation: The above mentioned table T3 explained that Instructional leadership is significantly and positively related to teachers' job performance and organization citizenship behavior with ($\beta=.45$, $p=.012$; $\beta=.39$, $p=.004$) respectively. These values depicted that H1 & H2 accepted.

Mediation Analysis

Table 4:Mediation Analysis H3 & H4

Sr#	Hypotheses	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	Results
H3	IL → SE → TJP	.45	.32	.008	.061	Partial Mediation
		$P > .05$	$P < .01$			
H4	IL → SE → OCB	.39	.28	.013	.005	Partial Mediation
		$P < .05$	$P > .01$			

Note: Bootstrap sample size 5000. LL = lower limit; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit; IL= instructional leadership. SE= self-efficacy, TJB=teachers' job performance, OCB=organization citizenship behavior

Interpretation: The mediation analysis is shown in the table above, and it was posited that self-efficacy serves as a mediating variable in the relationship between IL and TJB. Results from H3 showed that there is a partial mediation because the relationship between instructional leaders and performance is significant in the presence of self-efficacy ($\beta=0.32$, $p .01$) and insignificant in the direct path ($\beta =.45$, $p > .05$). H 3 is therefore approved. The mediation analysis was shown in the table above, and it was suggested that self-efficacy serves as a mediating variable in the relationship between IL and OCB. Results from H4 showed that there is a significant relationship between instructional leaders and citizenship in the presence of self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.28$, $p .01$), as well as a significant relationship in the direct path ($\beta =.39$, $p > .05$), demonstrating partial mediation consequently, H4 is accepted.

Discussion

This study aims to identify the direct and indirect effects of instructional leadership on self-efficacy among college/school level teaching staff, including teachers/lecturers and professors, as well as job performance and citizenship behaviour. The findings of this study are consistent with Sulistiya's (2013) research, which found that principal leadership had a significant impact on teacher performance. I also concur with Ngiodé's (2016) analysis of the research results, which showed that the leadership of the principal has a favourable and significant effect on teacher performance. Previous studies have demonstrated the importance of "leadership" in fostering environments that inspire, involve, and sustain teachers' professional development (Zheng et al., 2018). Our research suggests that strong instructional leadership contributes to the effectiveness of teaching staff by increasing their capacity to design learning environments in both the public and private sectors (Clarke & O'Donoghue, 2017; Hallinger, 2018). Recently, changes have been made to how teachers and principals perform their roles in the educational system (Arar, 2017). There has been an increase in teacher autonomy as a result of the transition from outdated educational reforms, which suggests that potential instructors who possess strong leadership qualities behave civically in the workplace and enhance organization citizenship behavior (Somech and Oplatka, 2014). Our findings contribute to the literature by investigating the direct impact of instructional leaders' roles on OCB, which is consistent with other recent research on different leadership styles such as transformational and transactional leadership (Coyne et al., 2013).

According to Tuan (2016), encourages employees to go above and beyond the scope of their job descriptions. The third research question looks into whether teacher self-efficacy affects the relationship between instructional leadership and job performance. Effective instructional leadership methods provide incentives for teachers, promote professional development, maintain high visibility, and make instructors feel valued

(Hallinger, 2013). Teachers who are highly effective perform better. Bandura (1977) also supports the current finding of employee leaders' high efficacy in creating a healthy work environment and performance level. Additionally, prior research has demonstrated a strong correlation between a better understanding of teachers' effectiveness and school leadership, which enhances teachers' progress (Fackler & Malmberg, 2016). Our results are in line with earlier research that validates the theoretical contribution of teaching staff efficacy as a link between instructional leadership and job performance, both at the school level and in the context of Pakistan's high-secondary educational system. High efficacy teachers complied with the directives of their principals or leaders, feeling more supported and going above and beyond the extra-role behaviours. A previous study (Dilekli & Tezci, 2016) found a link between teachers' self-efficacy and better classroom performance, as well as an inclusive educational system (Toy & Duru, 2016). Additionally, it is thought that teachers' efficacy may act as a mediator between distributive leadership and job integration as well as between leader-team interaction (Kavgac & Alk, 2017). (Kurt, 2016). Our statistical findings are fully supported by prior research, which also forecasts encouraging teachers' discretionary behaviours (Cayirdag, 2017).

Conclusion

This study looked at the relationship between instructional leadership, employee teacher performance, and OCB in Pakistani and State of Azad Jammu Kashmir educational institutions. The findings showed that leadership has a positive influence on teachers' performance and free-will choices. These findings also help us understand that, in order to succeed in the educational sector and community development on a national and international level, it is necessary to employ leadership techniques and strategies similar to those used in other important areas of the economy. Since there are many different aspects of leadership, we must think about the appropriate leadership techniques to improve teachers' learning. Our study contributes to the body of knowledge regarding the causal link between highly regarded ILs and superior teacher job performance, as well as between instructional leadership and OCB. We identified a mechanism by which teachers' self-efficacy links the performance and instruction of leaders. High teacher self-efficacy is also believed to act as a mediator between organisational citizenship behaviour and instructional leadership.

Theoretical Implications

According to recent statistical findings, principal instructional leadership has a significant impact on students' learning (Heck & Hallinger, 2014). This study also shows that students do not learn directly from highly effective teachers. Similar to other research on leadership styles (Chon and Zoltan, 2019) and sectors (Newman et al., 2017), this study also discovers a direct link between instructional leaders/principals and teachers' civic behaviour. Through their leadership abilities, instructional leaders at colleges and universities contribute to higher levels of OCB in teachers. Additionally, this work advances scientific knowledge by including self-efficacy as a mediating mechanism in the relationship between instructional leaders and teacher performance, as well as between instructional leaders and OCB (Mahipalan, Sheena & Muhammed, 2019).

Practical Implications

Education is regarded as one of the most prestigious areas of the economy in any society, and in Pakistan it is crucial to raise the literacy rate and lower inflation. The results of this study have significant ramifications for the broader field of administrative and management practises in education. First, school superintendents and college presidents, as well as their management teams, should promote this style of leadership more within their institutions, given the crucial role that it can play in enhancing teacher performance in the workplace. Education ministers of universities and colleges, as well as their HR managers, should concentrate on implementing formal HRM procedures (such as training and development, and performance evaluation systems), in order to promote this type of leadership because it may not come naturally to principals. The idea of leadership practices should be promoted, and various training programmes and seminars should be held to include their participants. While principals should be accountable for acting like a leader rather than following the conventional school of thought by getting involved in the growth of the community and society as a whole, not just in one area.

Limitations of the Study

Research on the impact of instructional leadership on job performance and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) with the mediating role of self-efficacy faces several limitations, some of which are:

1. **Generalizability:** The findings of research on this topic may not be applicable to all contexts and populations. The results may be limited to specific settings, such as a particular industry or culture, and may not be generalizable to other contexts or populations.
2. **Causality:** It is challenging to establish causality in this type of research. While instructional leadership may have a positive impact on self-efficacy, job performance, and OCB, other factors such as personality traits, motivation, and organizational culture may also influence these outcomes.

3. Measurement: Self-efficacy, job performance, and OCB are complex constructs that are difficult to measure accurately. Self-efficacy, in particular, is often measured through self-reported surveys, which may be subject to biases and may not reflect actual behavior.

4. Mediation effect: While self-efficacy may mediate the relationship between instructional leadership and job performance and OCB, it is possible that other variables may also play a role in this relationship. For example, other forms of leadership, such as transformational leadership, may also impact self-efficacy, job performance, and OCB.

5. Long-term effects: Research on this topic often focuses on short-term outcomes. However, the long-term effects of instructional leadership on job performance and OCB, with the mediating role of self-efficacy, are not well understood. It is possible that the effects may vary over time and may not be sustained in the long run.

6. Reverse causation: It is possible that self-efficacy may influence instructional leadership rather than the other way around. For example, if employees have high self-efficacy, they may seek out and respond better to instructional leadership. In this case, self-efficacy may be the cause of instructional leadership rather than the other way around.

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